

EXPLORATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF POOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS ON SANTIAGO AND MANOLIN IN AN ECONOMICALLY DEPRIVED CUBAN SOCIETY IN *THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA*

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Abstract:

This paper's assiduous concern is to take the wraps off the influence of poor socio-economic conditions on Santiago and Manolin of an economically deprived Cuban society through the delineation of their poverty-stricken lives in Ernest Miller Hemingway's novella *The Old Man and the Sea*. The then poor socio-economic conditions of the Cuban society snatches the beautiful moments of the old man's life and it turns him into a formidable man who vehemently invigorates him to undergo the untold sea-suffering out in the deep sea. On the other hand, Manolin's life is also influenced and associated with that poor society which compels Manolin's parents to send him to fishing boats instead of sending to school. The long tiring and challenging fishing activities are the barriers to the way of his education resulting from economic deprivation of the Cuban society. Throughout the whole of the novella, Santiago shows serious courage and assiduousness and leaves no stone unturned to catch a fish in order to kick away his poverty. Though he was unable to catch any fish for eighty-four-days, he was not disappointed at all. He relentlessly endures marine aches and pains in the deep sea for days. Poverty ingrains intense firmness and incredible strength in his inner faculty to fight against it.

Keywords: poverty, poor socio-economic conditions, deprivation of education, fishing, struggle

1. Introduction

The Old Man and the Sea attracts attention from all quarters of the world. It has been most debated for its portrayal of characters and its themes. Amongst the variable themes, this paper gives an account of how Santiago and Manolin's lives are influenced by the poor socio-economic conditions prevalent in the then Cuban society in *The Old Man and the Sea*. As the

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literature is the imitation of the real life (Abrams, 197). "It also focuses on how they both share a bonding which helps them struggle against the existing problems in the society. It is the story of a Cuban fisherman, Santiago, whose sole motto for life is, "A man can be destroyed but not defeated." (Hemingway, 2013, p.90). Eighty-four days of futile efforts gain him the title of 'salao', the worst form of bad luck. The novella became particularly popular for the diverse themes it included. The story revolves around Santiago's struggle for existence as a skillful fisherman." (Corbett, Bob, 2006). We find the same struggle in *The Life of Pi* and in the story of a spider and King Bruce.

For the sake of our exploratory discussion, this paper analyzes the socio-economic and cultural atmosphere of the then Cuban society that will help us a lot unfold the reasons for their poverty. "Cuba had a one-crop economy (sugar cane) whose domestic market was constructed. Its population was characterized by chronic unemployment and deep poverty. United States monopolies like Bethlehem Steel Corporation and Speyer gained control over valuable national resources. The banks and the country's entire financial system, all electric power production and the majority of industry were dominated by US companies. US monopolies owned 25 percent of the best land in Cuba. More than 80 percent of farmland was owned by sugar and livestock." (<http://www.sjsu.edu/faculty/watkins/cuba.htm>).

Manolin is a young man who is tremendously hand in glove with Santiago who has spent several years by teaching and instructing him on the traditional methods of fishing. Together they are a separate world. "Santiago does not treat Manolin as a young boy but rather as an equal." (McGuire). He serves him and takes care of the old man without caring of what his parents would say. Every day he brings back Santiago's boat after the old man's worldly ordeals. Unlike most of the children of his age, he finds solace in the company of his old friend discussing issues of common interest. As Cubans lived in the countryside, they lived in abysmal poverty. "Below I have compromised a chart of some statistics that illustrates poverty in Cuba prior to 1959. More than 50% had no toilets of any kind 45% of the rural population was illiterate, 85% had no inside running water. 25% of the labor force was unemployed. 91% had no electricity. 27% of urban children did not attend school. 1 doctor per 2,000 people in rural area, 75% of rural dwellings was huts made from palm trees." (<http://www.democraticunderground.com>).

In Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea*, it is Santiago who continues to fish. Like Lord Jim, Santiago is also pitched into the dangerous ocean all alone and solitary pitted against the cruel forces of nature represented by fish, the shark and in the bird. He never frustrates or breaks down in the face of great challenges as a man doesn't quit struggling against the problems of life. The Myth of Sisyphus is duly related to the heroic but doomed struggle against the existing problems found in *The Old Man and the Sea*. On the other hand, Manolin is a young man who is closely intimate with Santiago who has spent several years by teaching and instructing him on the traditional methods of fishing. The poor socio-economic conditions of the then Cuban society compels Santiago to go to the deep sea for fishing even in his old age, and on the other hand, Manolin's parents send him in different fishing boats to secure livelihood. The purpose of this paper is also to expose how Santiago and Manolin's lives are greatly influenced by the poor socio-economic conditions of Cuban society in *The Old Man and the Sea*. So, it can finally be said that the influence of poor socio-economic conditions on Santiago and Manolin is, in fact, worth talking.

2. Methodology

In qualitative research method, taking into account of the influence of poor socio-economic conditions, economically deprived Cuban society, the untold sea-suffering, Santiago's mental and physical hardships, chronic unemployment and deep poverty, domination of US companies, US monopolies owned 25 percent Cuban land, 90 percent of the country's raw sugar and tobacco exported to the US, poor education, malnourishment and hunger, huts made from palm trees, Manolin's steering clear of schooling, *The Act of Will*, *The Old Man and the Sea*, *Daridro*, a poem by Nazrul, *Lord Jim*, *King Bruce*, *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner*, *The Myth of Sisyphus*, *The Life of Pi*, *Out, Out* and some websites have been done applying different sort of techniques and methods to find out the influence of poor socio-economic condition on Santiago and Manolin in an economically deprived Cuban society in *The Old Man and the Sea* hidden in words, phrases and sentences. Many research articles and books written on these very concerned issues have been sometimes summarized and sometimes analyzed through empirical observations for collecting data from direct and indirect sources to demonstrate our findings.

2.1 The then socio-economic conditions through the poverty of Santiago

As Ernest Miller Hemingway was born in Illinois in 1899 (Friends Book Corner, 2013 reprint: 2013), he witnessed his surroundings with his naked eyes very critically which imparted a great influence upon his inner faculty. He tried his best to portray all of the bitter truths through his writings. As he was a keen social observer, he saw social inequality everywhere in the Cuban society. In regard to this phenomenon, we can certainly claim that poor socio-economic conditions of an economically deprived Cuban society are the most burning questions in Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea* and it is picturesquely delineated through Santiago who undergoes a series of mental and physical hardships only because of his poor socio-economic condition. Santiago does all-out efforts to catch fish initially with Manolin and then alone in a great ocean so that he can keep the flag flying against the poverty. Poverty has made "*The old man thin and gaunt with deep wrinkles in the back of his neck.*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.5). Santiago continues fishing not only drinking the cup of sorrow but also using the traditional methods because of not having enough money to buy modern fishing tools. These traditional tools do not help him catch enough fish. Thus, he is forced to live a semi-impooverished life. The description of his belongings proves his impoverishment which is portrayed through "*The shack that was made of the tough bug shields of the royal palm which are called guano and in it there was a bed, a table, one chair, and a place on the dirt floor to cook with charcoal*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.11).

2.2 Santiago's suffering in the deep sea makes him uncompromising

He fights tooth and nail to keep all odds of the hard existence of living conditioned by the social and cultural structures that mark his poverty-afflicted life. He faces some conflicts with nature because of leaping in the dark of mighty sea. He remains 84 days in his small fishing boat without getting any fish. Finally, he hooks a gigantic 18 feet long swordfish. The combat

then begins and the fish drags the small boat and Santiago far out to sea. For two days they strive, and Santiago wins it. But he loses the great fish on the way home to the scavenger sharks who find the Marlin an easy prey. The life-and-death battle is helpless for the old man but he is tremendously determined to fight against the sharks. He says, "*Fish,*" he said softly, aloud, "*I'll stay with you until I am dead.*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.44). Throughout the whole story, Santiago shows serious courage and assiduousness and leaves no stone unturned to catch a fish in order to kick away poverty. On the contrary, the old man in *The Old and the Sea* seems to be in no mood to compromise at all and, thus, never thinks of bidding farewell to the fish at any stage. Fearlessness comes out of its own when one is free from attachment to wealth, reputation, health and so on, but true is free from superstitions and delusion, pursues his formidable assignment wholeheartedly, and his hopeful stances really amazing as S.T. Coleridge also points out:

*"Where no hope is, life is a warning that only
Serves to make us grieve when we are old"*

(Coleridge ST. 1993).

To make both ends meet, he goes through fire and water due to marine aches and pains in the sweltering heat of the sun for hours. The struggles that Santiago has to go through were not easy, but the old man always believes in himself that he would be able to overcome them. We find the same struggle in *The Life of Pi*. Pi goes out at sea with many animals and passes many days facing difficulties, other animals, and nature. "*The story deals with an epic struggle between an old experienced fisherman and the greatest catch of his life. The first novel The Old Man and the Sea deals with the adventures and struggle faced by an old man in the sea. 'Life of Pi by Yann Martel is a Canadian fantasy adventure novel. It deals with the adventures and struggles faced by Piscine Molitor "Pi" Patel.*" (Kiefer, Jonathan, 2002).

2.3 Strong determination to kick away poverty

It is Santiago's 'unconquerable spirit to defeat poverty which gives him the ability to struggle and persevere against the hardship of life. At one stage, though the Marlin takes away his harpoon, Santiago said, "*A man can be destroyed but not defeated*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.90). Poverty ingrains so much moral quality of endurance in his inner faculty that he even admires the fish for its strife. Furthermore, during his battle with the fish and the sharks, Santiago shows his infinite and fantabulous endurance and incredible strength. "*Santiago's endeavor to kill the fish parallels the struggle contained in the story of a spider and King Bruce because like Bruce, he tries again and again without yielding to the adverse circumstances and hard times.*" (Shams, Ishtiaque: 2004). He retains his own integrity in the face of great challenge; he exhausts himself in a good fight. A man doesn't quit. The Myth of Sisyphus is uniquely apropos. "*Like Camus, the novelist Ernst Hemingway suggests that the human struggle against futility gives life meaning. His novel, The Old Man and the Sea illustrates the unwavering human dignity that empowers Sisyphus to continuously roll his boulder up the hill and drives the protagonist of his novel, Santiago to grip the fishing line with unparalleled resolve. Santiago is an impoverished*

elderly fisherman who is barely able to care for himself without the aid of a young boy. When he hooks a monstrous fish, he holds steadfast onto the fishing line and is dragged out on the ocean for two days." (Eddins, Dwight, *Of Rocks and Marlin*) Santiago is tremendously determined to endure the pain just like the American player Joe DiMaggio. Sometimes poverty and pains make a man more determined and stronger to fulfill his goal. Even it can make a man great fighter against all odds and oddities. Thus, the poor socio-economic conditions have made Santiago more determined and stronger. Our rebel poet Kazi Nazrul Islam also praises the positive power of poverty of making a man great in his poem Daridro. He says, "*Hey poverty, you have made me great.*" (Islam, Kazi Nazrul, Sanchhita: 2013, page 103). The old man declares that he must have confidence and he must be worthy of the great DiMaggio who does all things perfectly even with the pain of the bone spur in his heel. Actually, he moves from heaven to earth to maintain his day to day livelihood. Hemingway draws his reader's attention to this through Santiago's continual attempt to catch a fish for about three months. "*Suffering is another mean that can be considered as a first and final inevitable task of man.*" (Assagioli, Robert. *The Act of Will*, Viking Press, USA, 1973 & source)

2.4 Faith enabling him to be positive and patient amid difficulties

Though Santiago is living in an extremely untold poverty-stricken society with nothing to eat, he is still able to remain optimistic. He passes the most perilous time but he does not hesitate to have faith in God Who helps him undergo and bell the cat against all the sufferings. In the same way, it is his strong faith that enables him to build up a strong brotherhood between him and his surroundings. He tries heart and soul to pick the fish on his boat. It exhausts him. "*I am a tired old man,' he says, 'but I have killed this fish which is my brother and now I must do the slave work'*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.82). It is his faith that makes him feel guilty. It also makes him think that it is perhaps a sin to kill the fish. Therefore, Santiago's faith in DiMaggio and God help him find the necessary courage to undergo a hard life and a terrible battle against the Marlin and the sharks. It is the poor socio-economic conditions that make him endurable, patient, fighter, positive, strong, determined and courageous. He passes through sufferings and pains with great dignity and determination by remembering that every day is a new day. He has physical strength and patience which induce him to think that "*pain does not matter to a man*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.73).

2.5 The grave picture of Santiago's possession

The grave picture of the then Cuban poor economic conditions has been delineated through the picturing of Santiago's shack that is barely furnished with a cooking place on the dirt floor. The shack is organic, made from palm trees. His mast is almost as long as his shack is wide. Sometimes he uses papers and trousers to make the pillow as he cannot afford to buy it because of lacking money. Ernest Hemingway says, "*He rolled his trousers up to make a pillow, putting the newspaper inside them.*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.19). Though he has been working hard to turn over a new leaf keeping the wolf from the door since time immemorial, he has only been able to possess a small shack, a table, a chair, a bed and a dirty floor to cook with charcoal. He has no water, soap, and towel. He is so hard up that he can't afford a jacket for

the winter. He goes for fishing on barefoot because of having no shoes. When he was in the sea, he had a bottle of water for the day. He has no food but every day he pretends of possessing "*A pot of yellow rice with fish*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.11). He is so poor that he cannot buy a pillow, a shirt, and warm clothes. He has a shirt but it has so many patches that it seems the sail. Seeing the destitute and vulnerable condition of the old man, Manolin talks to himself, "*I must get him another shirt and a jacket for the winter and some sort of shoes and another blanket*" (Hemingway, 2013, p. 15-16).

2.6 Impact of changing the socio-economic pattern on fishing

However, the novella does reflect a universal pattern of socioeconomic change familiar even today among developing nations. In rural Cuba of the 1930s and 1940s, the traditional fishing culture began shifting to the material progress of a fishing industry dependent on the industrialized world for its livelihood, environmentally oblivious or negligent, increasingly reliant on mechanized methods to ensure profit, and much less bound to extended families and local communities. At that time, the process of concentrated manufacturing had grown, and the control of foreign capital had expanded. In addition, the monopoly held by large businesses extended to the farming areas, with the consequent displacement of small farmers. This was only partly offset by the high cost of new agronomical techniques to increase yields, such as the use of fertilizers or catch crop systems.

(<http://www.sjsu.edu/faculty/watkins/cuba.htm>).

2.7 Struggling to reestablish his identity in the poverty-afflicted society

In this novella, Hemingway depicts Santiago as a dedicated fisherman tries to reestablish his own identity in the poverty-stricken society. The novella is truly about the plight of an old man struggling against poverty to maintain his identity and dignity though he is over head and ears in difficulties. He wants to reestablish his reputation in the community. Santiago does not look to any outside agency to come to him to rescue and provides him with physical strength. He draws moral strength by his own utterance addressed to himself while he is fighting with the unconquerable forces of nature after killing the fish, Marlin. "*In modern fiction, it is Melville, Fitzgerald, Faulkner, and Conrad who put considerable the themes Hemingway's fictional works. Like Lord Jim, Santiago is also pitched into the dangerous ocean all alone and solitary pitted against the cruel forces of nature represented by fish, the shark the bird as a temptation to create some slackness in his concentration. The sharks are the symbol of evil representing evil forces against which man is always pitted.*" (Levin, Harry, 1962).

2.8 Manolin's risky apprenticeship under Santiago for learning fishing

The clutches of poor socio-economic conditions in the Cuban society were so much that the children of various ages seek work for their livelihood. So, Manolin has also been fishing with Santiago since he was a child of five years old. He is Santiago's devoted apprentice. He accepts hard work happily, never complains. He is still in his adolescence but he has to choose the most venturesome path of being Santiago's apprentice and devoted attendant steering clear of schooling. Manolin is very hard working. He gets up early in the morning

and helps the old man get the boat ready. Then, he has to get ready his boat for fishing all day long. Nearly destroying his best part of his life, he goes to the deep sea with the old Man for fishing. He is a boy who helps the old man, Santiago, on his fishing boat for a long time. His age is to be attached with his school, going to the friends and books but he is emotionally attached to the old man because the old man has taught him how to fish, and so the boy loves him from the core of his heart.

2.9 The friendship between Santiago and Manolin

The old man is a hero for the boy, and so he is devoted to him. He helps him and serves him like a son or a child worker. He offers the old man a beer, brings sardines and fresh baits for the old man. Manolin is very careful of the service of Santiago. He looks after his shack. Each morning, he waits for his returning. He serves coffee to the old man when he returns from the fishing. He always consoles the old man in his desperation and tells that *"now we fish together again"*. (Hemingway, 2013, p.109). Manolin is the hope of Santiago. He wants to go with the Old Man again because they made some money yesterday. He fulfills the social as well as physical needs of Santiago by bringing him the newspaper, food and carrying his lines. The old man thinks of the boy while fighting the fish: *"I wish the boy was here."* (Hemingway, 2013, p.42) He really misses the company of the youth during his eighty-fifth travels in the sea which results in another failure from a utilitarian point of view.

2.10 Society turns Manolin into a child labor

Poverty, child labor, and educational deprivation produce a self-reinforcing cycle of disadvantages. The long hours laboring by Manolin in hazardous fishing circumstances are another barrier to the way of achieving an education. *"The term 'child labor' is often defined as work that deprives children of their childhood, their potential, and their dignity, and that is harmful to physical and mental development"* (Ilo.org). It is undoubtedly risky for his health and safety. It hampers societal progress, too. The same risky child labor is found in Robert Frost's *Out, Out*. Robert Frost says,

*"Since he was old enough to know, big boy
Doing a man's work, though a child at heart" —*

"Here we see how the boy in the poem still young at heart and although he was physically strong enough to carry out such a dangerous job, growing up in a farming society, he was expected to do this. Jobs on a farm were to determine his livelihood for the rest of his life."

(<https://artscolumbia.org/literary-arts/poetry/poem-out-out-by-robert-frost-analysis-45928/>)

It is widely acknowledged that child labor is commonly associated with poverty. Poverty compels the parents to withdraw Manolin from school and send him to work. But he engages himself as a fishing laborer because education is unaffordable, inaccessible or seems to be irrelevant. Household poverty is the primary driver of child laborer and other forces are also at play. At one stage, Manolin is compelled to leave Santiago by his father who sends him to a fisherman who he believes to be better skilled than him. Manolin obeys him but

does not abandon. Manolin is seen to be most content when he's around his true mentor. Unlike most of the children of his age, he finds solace in the company of his old friend discussing issues of common interest. Age does not impede with their bonding with each other. Now the boy has moved on to another boat, a more successful one, at his parents' behest, but he intends to work with Santiago. Nonetheless, Manolin's respect and affection for the old man lead him to care for Santiago and provide basic essentials for him. Manolin is captivated not only by the old man's abilities as a deep-sea fisherman but also his recounting of past heroic adventures; his 'knowledge' of American Baseball and its contemporary hero, Joe DiMaggio. (<http://www.pearsonschoolsandfecolleges.co.uk/>).

2.11 Evil power of poverty

It is undoubtedly risky for his health and safety. It hampers societal progress, too. However, after Santiago went forty days without catching any fish, Manolin's parents moved him to a different fishing boat that had better luck. Manolin tells Santiago, "*It was papa made me leave. I am a boy and I must obey him.*" (Hemingway, 2013, p.6). On top of that, he is sent to other fishing boats so that he can catch big fish "*and the boy had gone at their orders to another boat which caught three good fish the first week.*" (Hemingway 2013, p.5). In the poverty-stricken Cuban society, even parents used to force their children to join various workforces to add some money to their poor income. Manolin should have respect and affection for education and school but he shows interest in fishing activities because of the cruel clutches of poor socio-economic conditions of the then Cuban society.

3. Conclusion

After a long strenuous study, it has been found that *The Old Man and the Sea* is a magnificent story exploring the influence of poor socio-economic conditions of the then Cuban society. There is a side table as well. In fact, Hemingway in his novella explicates the individual, the struggle for the most basic existence, the battle with extreme poverty for survival itself. But most importantly, he makes one acknowledge the cruel picture of poverty through the friendship of Santiago and Manolin. The picture of Diligence, struggling, perseverance, battle with the Marlin, going out deep sea and power of nature, friendship has been highlighted but all these things have got immense influence because of one thing that is poverty. The influence of poor socio-economic conditions of the then Cuban society compels Santiago to go to the deep sea for fishing even in his old age, and on the other hand, Manolin's parents send him in different fishing boats to secure livelihood.

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